

Triad 1 - (Selection number 2): Coverture, Social Security Amendments, Equal Protection Revolution

Coverture refers to the historical legal doctrine that forced women to assume her husband's legal identity after marriage, limiting her legal rights. The Social Security Amendments of 1939 expanded benefits for certain groups (wives and children of deceased or retired male workers), but inadvertently reinforced the idea of marital unity and coverture, disproportionately benefiting men in marriages. The equal protection revolution emerged in the early 1970s, working to dismantle discriminatory practices and secure equal rights for women, including dismantling remnants of coverture.

Conceptually, these terms are interconnected as they all pertain to women's rights and status within the context of marriage and state benefits. Coverture and the Social Security Amendments, despite being products of different time periods, both served to perpetuate the subordination of women within the institution of marriage. Coverture explicitly rendered women as dependents with limited legal rights, while the Social Security Amendments inexplicitly reinforced gendered expectations by incentivizing men to marry and women to stay home, thus maintaining the power dynamics of coverture. On the other hand, the equal protection revolution represents a shift in society's understanding of women's rights and a concerted effort to dismantle the remnants of coverture. This period saw significant legal and political changes that aimed to challenge the legacy of coverture and create a more egalitarian society. The relationship between coverture, Social Security Amendments, and the equal protection revolution demonstrates a historical progression from the subjugation of women within marriage to a movement advocating for equal rights and opportunities.

Triad 2 - (Selection Number 4): Bowers v Hardwick, Act Up, Lawrence v. Texas

Bowers v. Hardwick was a Supreme Court case that upheld Georgia's sodomy law, sparking outrage and inspiring activism in the LGBTQ+ community. Act Up was a grassroots activist organization that successfully challenged the government's inaction on AIDS research and treatment, demonstrating the power of direct action in influencing public opinion and policy.

Lawrence v. Texas (2003) was a landmark Supreme Court case that overturned sodomy laws in the United States, signifying a shift in legal and societal attitudes towards LGBTQ+ rights.

The core concept connecting these three terms is the transformative power of resistance in the face of adversity. *Bowers v. Hardwick*, Act Up, and *Lawrence v. Texas* collectively illustrate the complex interplay of legal setbacks, grassroots activism, and eventual legal victories in shaping LGBTQ+ rights in the United States. These three terms reveal how resistance to oppression can foster change and reshape societal norms. *Bowers v. Hardwick* exposed the legal system's failure to protect LGBTQ+ rights, igniting a sense of urgency for collective action. Act Up showcased the potential for grassroots activism to reshape societal attitudes and policies, paving the way for a more inclusive society. Finally, *Lawrence v. Texas*, influenced by the work of activists and gay studies scholars, symbolized a legal victory that reflected the change in societal norms and attitudes towards LGBTQ+ rights.

**Triad 3 - (Selection Number 5): Lynching/Jim Crow, Anita Hill,
*Loving v. Virginia***

Lynching/Jim Crow refers to racial violence and segregation, targeting primarily African Americans, perpetuating systemic discrimination. Anita Hill, an African American woman, testified before the Senate Judiciary Committee against Clarence Thomas, a Supreme Court nominee in 1991, shedding light on workplace sexual harassment, especially for women of color. *Loving v. Virginia* was a groundbreaking Supreme Court decision that abolished laws prohibiting interracial marriage.

The conceptual link between these terms lies in their demonstration of the power of individual and collective action in challenging deeply entrenched discriminatory practices. Lynching/Jim Crow, Anita Hill, and *Loving v. Virginia* collectively illustrates the resilience and determination of marginalized communities in confronting and dismantling systemic discrimination. The resilience of marginalized communities can be observed in the fight against the brutal legacy of lynching and Jim Crow laws, Anita Hill's courage in confronting workplace sexual harassment and testifying before an unfriendly and unwelcoming Senate Committee, and successful efforts that led to *Loving v. Virginia's* groundbreaking defeat of racist laws.

Triad 4 - (Selection Number 8): *Scott v. Macy*, EEOC, Don't Ask/Don't Tell

Scott v. Macy is a court case which found that a person could not be denied federal employment solely based on their sexual orientation. The EEOC (Equal Employment Opportunity Commission) is a federal agency that enforces laws prohibiting workplace discrimination, including on the basis of sex. Don't Ask, Don't Tell was a military policy that prohibited openly gay, lesbian, and bisexual individuals from serving in the U.S. armed forces.

The central theme connecting these three terms is the continuous struggle for equality and recognition of LGBTQ+ and women's rights in various professional contexts. These terms demonstrate how legal decisions and policy changes have shaped the experiences of women and LGBTQ+ individuals particularly within the context of the workplace and the U.S. military. *Scott v. Macy* marked an early victory for LGBTQ+ employment rights, challenging the notion that one's sexual orientation should determine their professional opportunities. The EEOC's enforcement of anti-discrimination laws further solidified the importance of workplace equality, ensuring that women are protected from discrimination in various employment contexts. However, the enactment of Don't Ask, Don't Tell represented a setback in the fight for LGBTQ+ rights within the military and their broad position within society, as it forced LGBTQ+ service members to hide their true selves. These terms demonstrate the progress that has been made on behalf of women and LGBTQ+ rights, despite the setbacks encountered.

Essay 1 (Selection 1):

The tensions between radical and mainstream AIDS activism were a necessary catalyst for progress, as the two approaches complemented each other in addressing different aspects of the epidemic. Throughout the 1980s, when the AIDS epidemic hit and queer people had little political power, the AIDS activist movement was divided into radical and mainstream elements that, despite their differences, worked together to reshape the response to the crisis and foster collaboration and innovation within their community.

The radical activists, exemplified by organizations such as ACT UP, played a crucial role in raising public awareness and demanding urgency in the response to the epidemic. Their confrontational tactics, such as staging protests and die-ins, forced the media, government, and pharmaceutical companies to pay attention to the crisis (April 5 lecture, Dr. Canaday). This visibility and pressure created by these radical activists exposed the shortcomings of the existing response, which helped pave the way for more effective policies and treatments.

On the other hand, mainstream organizations and initiatives, like the Stop AIDS Project, focused on education, prevention, and collaboration with governmental and scientific institutions. Their approach was more cooperative, aiming to build bridges with key stakeholders and working within existing systems to advance research and policy, a much more 'mainstream' approach (April 5 lecture, Dr. Canaday). While their methods were less attention-grabbing than those of the radical activists, they played a crucial role in facilitating advancements in medical research and treatment, such as the development of antiretroviral therapy. Their efforts were, in part, aided and advanced because of the sense of urgency toward this issue, developed through efforts from the radical wing.

Drawing from the lectures, it becomes clear that the radical and mainstream aspects of AIDS activism played complementary roles in shaping the response to the epidemic. This dynamic is further exemplified in the assigned readings. For instance, "The Normal Heart" vividly captures the frustration and anger of those who faced not only a devastating health crisis but also systemic homophobia and neglect. By illustrating the critical role radical activism played in demanding a more aggressive response to the epidemic, this work emphasizes the essential function radical elements served in creating a sense of urgency and pushing for change.

In contrast, D'Emilio's article on Bayard Rustin provides an example of how an individual's activism can evolve over time in response to shifting political climates and personal experiences. While Rustin's career didn't specifically focus on AIDS activism, he was involved in a wide variety of social movements. However, his actions, efforts, and successes demonstrate the importance of engaging directly with the political process and working collaboratively with various stakeholders to achieve meaningful progress. This notion aligns with the role of mainstream AIDS activists, who aimed to build alliances and work within existing systems to

enact policy and drive tangible progress. Through Rustin's example, we see the value of combining radical activism's urgency with the practicality of mainstream approaches to create meaningful change in society. Understanding that his efforts benefited from the increased visibility of certain issues contributes to the idea that the two approaches work complementary.

The interplay between the radical and mainstream elements of the AIDS movement was essential in achieving significant progress. While the radical activists created a sense of urgency and pushed for change, the mainstream organizations provided the resources and connections necessary to translate these demands into tangible advancements. This multifaceted approach allowed the movement to more effectively address their needs from public perception to scientific research and policy implementation.

Essay 2 (Selection 3):

The intricate dance between state power and societal norms has, throughout history, shaped the landscape of gender and sexuality in profound ways. In the United States, the 20th century witnessed a dramatic shift in the state's role in regulating and influencing these aspects of life, with Dr. Canaday providing an insightful framework that characterizes this era as marked by periods of "Loosening," "Tightening," and "Resistance." This framework offers a compelling lens through which to examine the American state's impact on matters of gender and sexuality, capturing the essence of each period and the progressive arc of LGBT history.

However, this essay aims to extend Dr. Canaday's original thesis by proposing a slightly modified framework, redefining the third period as "Reversing" rather than "Resistance." This modification is not meant to discredit Dr. Canaday's analysis but rather to emphasize the transformative nature of this time as the American state began to dismantle many of the oppressive actions initiated during the "Tightening" period. Examining the American state's interventions through the adapted framework of "Loosening," "Tightening," and "Reversing" allows us to gain a deeper understanding of the complex dynamics that have shaped the history of gender and sexuality over the course of the 20th century and better appreciate the resilience and adaptability of the LGBTQ+ community and its allies in pushing for progress.

The early 20th century marked a period of "loosening" in the American state's intervention in matters of gender and sexuality. During this time, the government was less restrictive, allowing alternative gender roles and sexual relationships to flourish. The absence of significant state intervention enabled the rise of early queer subcultures, which thrived in urban environments like Greenwich Village and Harlem. This was all happening despite the existence of anti-sodomy laws in some regions, which were loosely enforced. The absence of state interference that necessitated marriages and channeled support through families facilitated the emergence of new gender roles and alternative sexual relationships, such as the "New Woman" and the Heterodoxy movement (Dr. Canaday lecture, Feb. 1 & Feb. 6). Furthermore, the evolving medical understanding of homosexuality contributed to the growing acceptance of a more fluid understanding of sexual orientation. This era of "loosening" set the stage for subsequent periods of "tightening" and "reversing" in state intervention on matters of gender and sexuality.

The period from the 1930s to the 1960s can be characterized as one of "tightening" with respect to the American state's impact on matters of gender and sexuality. During this time, the government actively intervened in the lives of its citizens, promoting heteronormativity and demonizing homosexuality, ultimately reinforcing traditional gender roles and suppressing alternative forms of sexuality. During this time, as Dr. Canaday described in her March 1 lecture, the American state deployed both "carrots" and "sticks" to support heterosexual relationships and penalize homosexuality. Policies such as tax incentives, social security, and the GI bill promoted heterosexual marriage, while legislation like Executive Order 10450 explicitly targeted and

penalized homosexuals as security risks (Dr. Canaday lecture, March 1). The Lavender Scare, which emerged as a partisan attack against Democrats, further fueled the government's tightening grip on matters of gender and sexuality. It's clear the extent to which the government's increased scrutiny and persecution of homosexuals during this time significantly restricted their freedoms and available opportunities.

The third phase of the American state's impact on matters of gender and sexuality, characterized as a period of "reversal," ushered in a new era of resistance against previously established discriminatory policies. This period saw significant legal and social changes, as the government increasingly recognized the rights and liberties of individuals regardless of their sexual orientation or gender. The institutional changes began with the dismantling of sodomy laws, which had initially been sparingly enforced but had become more aggressive as a result of McCarthyist fears and the Lavender Scare (Dr. Canaday lecture, April 19). As the century progressed, many states began to repeal these laws, culminating in the landmark Supreme Court case *Lawrence v. Texas*. This decision invalidated sodomy laws across the nation, protecting the privacy rights and equal protection of homosexual individuals. The victory in *Lawrence v. Texas* opened the door for further advancements in the fight for equality. During the 1970s, the equal rights revolution began to break down legal barriers for women, reversing much of the government's discriminatory policies regarding gender, in areas such as Social Security law. These changes reflected the state's declining use of marriage as a tool for channeling benefits exclusively to heterosexual couples (Dr. Canaday lecture, April 19).

Dr. Canaday's original thesis describes this period as "resistance". However, in my opinion, exploring this period as a "reversal" rather than merely "resistance" offers a more comprehensive and nuanced understanding of the historical transformations that occurred during this time. By characterizing the third period as a "reversal," we emphasize the tangible accomplishments and victories for women and the LGBT community during this time, rather than solely focusing on the struggle against discriminatory policies. This shift in perspective allows us to appreciate the successful dismantling of long-standing oppressive governmental policies and the creation of a more equitable society. The term "reversal" also highlights the fact that these changes were not merely acts of defiance, but rather marked a genuine shift in the government's attitudes and actions towards gender and sexuality.

The American state's involvement in matters of gender and sexuality during the 20th century illustrates the dramatic changes that progressed from an era of relative leniency to one of increased regulation, culminating in a period of significant reversal. Adopting the concept of "reversal" as an extension of Dr. Canaday's thesis allows us to emphasize not only the ongoing struggle but also the impressive accomplishments that have reshaped our society. As we continue to champion equality, it is essential to appreciate this rich historical context and use it as a guide for further progress.